

FACTORS HAVING EFFECTS ON PEOPLE WHO DO ORIENTEERING SPORT IN TURKEY, START THIS SPORT AND THEIR EXPECTATIONS

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Abstract:

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to determine factors encouraging people who do orienteering sport in Turkey to start this sport and their expectations. **Material and Method:** The survey used in the study was developed Sunay and Saracoglu and was applied to other branches, and its validity and reliability were accepted (Sunay & Saracoglu, 2003). For this survey applied to orienteering branch, expert opinions were taken, and required regulations were done. This study was carried out with 258 people, who do orienteering sport and whose age average was $26,77 \pm 8.029$. Because data did not show normal distribution as a result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, "Non-parametric" test was used. For multiple comparisons Kruskal Wallis H test and Mann-Whitney U test and descriptive statistics in analysis of distinction between groups were used in the situations in which normality and homogeneity of variances were not provided. Significance level for comparisons was determined as $p < 0,05$. **Findings:** While friend and peer group was in the first place among factors encouraging people to start orienteering sport, effect of television channels on directing to sport was found very low. Among the reasons why they do the sport, liking orienteering sport is in the first place, and attending to a friend group is in the last places. While it has been seen that expectations of being chosen for National Team and playing for National Team are in the first places, expectations of being a referee are in the last places. When total points related to factors encouraging people to do sport, the reasons why they do sport and their expectations were evaluated, a significant difference between sex and sport years

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was not seen. A significant difference between the reasons why they do this sport and father's educational level was seen ($p < 0.05$). Between the reasons why they do this sport and father's educational level, a negative relation was seen. A significant difference between the reasons why they do this sport and father's profession. It was seen that individuals whose fathers were self-employment made for orienteering sport mostly. A significant relation between mother's profession, mother's educational level, sport year and factors encouraging people to do sport, the reasons why they do sport and their expectations was not determined. **Conclusion:** It is thought that positive approaches such as being chosen for national team and being a national player, friend and peer group and liking this branch provide positive contributions for individuals to make for orienteering branch.

Keywords: orienteering, sport, expectation, encouragement

1. Introduction

As orienteering may be applied in nature and many fields, it is done in many forms. Because of this feature, it has been a sport branch that is indigenised and performed willingly by many people nowadays.

It has gained great importance in our lives from past to present. Throughout the history, people marked their rotas of land, sea and air voyages on the map and reached their destinations by finding their directions with the help of compasses (Tanrıku, 2011). Orienteering is a sport branch that has spread quickly recently and that draws attention of many people from 7 to 70.

"Orienteering is a nature sport that can be performed on every sort of terrain and that athletes try to find the checkpoints with the help of maps and compasses. It is performed either individually or as a team and generally at forestlands. The aim of the athletes is to find the targets that are placed on the terrain and marked on the map previously, by running and with least mistake" (Karaca, 2013). With another description, orienteering is to use the skills of map reading in a flawless manner, complete concentration, and quick decision-making altogether by choosing the best rota between starting, check and finish points on mountainous and steep terrains. This open area hiking provides a unique and unbelievable experience (Güler, 2003). Orienteering is a pretty healthy sport that requires intelligence as well as activating the body. It doesn't only foster the physique, it also improves your thinking and problem-solving skills when you are under pressure and stress (Deniz et al., 2012).

The most important feature that differs orienteering from the other sports is that there isn't a leader to follow and a specified parkour. There are countless options that vary from athlete to athlete to reach the destination. There are many factors that matter alongside the physical features of the athletes (Tanrıku, 2011). Each sport has distinctive features. What differentiates orienteering from the other sports is to find and follow the most appropriate rota at an unknown area. Orienteering requires some skills

like map reading, evaluating the rota choice, the use of compass, concentration under stress, quick decision-making, and working at a natural terrain (IOF, 2011). Orienteering is a sport that is performed individually only on the terrain by using compass map and various techniques and tactics and following each target on the checkpoints one by one (Palıncuk et al., 2018). Orienteering is a lifelong activity. The educators can motivate the students and improve their physical activity by using orienteering (Beighle & Davst, 2004, cited by Hammes, 2007). It is also useful to use orienteering at physical education activities (Hammes, 2007).

2. Material and Method

The questionnaire that was used in the study was developed by Sunay and Saraçoğlu and was applied to the different branches and the validity and the reliability of the test was accepted (Sunay & Saraçoğlu, 2003). Expert opinions have been taken into consideration for this questionnaire that was adapted to the orienteering branch and necessary adjustments have been done. The study was applied to 258 orienteering sporters whose age average was $26,77 \pm 8.029$ in the 2018 season. Non-parametric methods were applied as the data didnt have a normality distribution after the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. When the homogeneity of normality and the variances weren't ensured, Kruskal Wallis H test was used for multiple comparisons, Mann-Whitney U test was used alongside with arithmetic mean and descriptive statics for binary groups. The significance level for comparisons was determined as $p < 0.05$.

3. Findings

Statistical values of the data about this study that was performed to show the factors encouraging people to do orienteering sport in Turkey and their expectations are represented on the table below.

Table 1: The results of significance level of factors encouraging for orienteering sport

The factors encouraging for the orienteering sport	$\bar{X}$	ss	Significance level
1. The family members' effect on encouraging for the sport	3,062	2,53459	3
2. The effect of the neighbourhood	3,876	1,61707	4
3. The effect of friends and peer group	2,8876	1,5071	1
4. The effect of the physical education teacher	3,031	1,85438	2
5. The effect of media organs	6,2209	1,60545	7
6. The effect of television channels	6,6899	1,83904	8
7. The effect of the sports facilities and equipmants at school	5,0465	1,5921	6
8. The effect of a trainor in the immediate surrounding	4,9186	1,95204	5

When we look at the significance level of the factors encouraging for orienteering sport, friend and peer group's effect is at the 1. level, the effect of the physical education teacher is at the 2. level and the effect of the family members is at the 3. level.

Table 2: The results of significance level of the reasons for doing orienteering

The reasons for doing orienteering	$\bar{X}$	ss	Significance level
9. To enhance financial situation	7,2597	2,39455	9
10. The interest in orienteering sport	2,5814	2,12891	1
11. The awareness of the positive contributions of the sport	4,2636	1,97856	3
12. To be involved in a friend group easily	6,8876	2,41593	8
13. To make use of their spare time	5,3721	2,0177	6
14. To be healthy by doing orienteering	4,469	1,73121	5
15. To gain prestige by friends as a sporter	4,2946	2,15509	4
16. To delight in succeeding	3,5853	2,58597	2
17. To act with a team spirit with friends	5,7636	2,43242	7

When we look at the significance levels for the reasons of doing orienteering, it has been seen that it is the interest in orienteering at the 1. level, to delight in succeeding at the 2. level, and the awarenees of the positive contributions of sport at the 3. level.

Table 3: The significance level of the expectations from the orienteering sport

The expectations from the orienteering	$\bar{X}$	ss	Significance level
18. To be and keep healthy	3,9922	3,00064	2
19. To have a good physical appearance	5,1628	2,2656	5
20. To have good relations with the community as a popular person	4,9302	2,41328	4
21. To be a good sporter and make a living of sports	4,8488	1,89111	3
22. To get a college education about sports in the future	6,124	2,12639	7
23. To be a trainer	5,9806	2,75942	6
24. To be a referee	7,1628	2,91725	10
25. To be a physical education teacher	6,2597	2,8364	8
26. To enhance financial situation	6,8101	2,78664	9
27. To attend the national team	2,6977	3,0061	1

When we look at the significance levels of the expectations from orienteering, it is seen that to attend the national team is at the 1. level, to be and keep healthy at the 2. level, and to be a good sporter and get a living of sports at the 3. level.

Table 4: Evaluating the education level of the father and the reasons for doing sport (Kruskal Wallis H)

The father's education level	n	Mean Rank	sd	$\bar{X}$	P	Significant difference
Primary School	52	122.58	2	7.87	0.19*	Between primary school and university, between high school and university
High School	106	123.37				
University	100	139.60				

p<0.05*

When we look at the evaluation of the reasons for doing sports and the education level of the father, it is seen that there is a significant difference in favor of those fathers whose education level is primary school (p<0.05).

Table 5: Evaluating the father's occupation and the expectations from the sport (Kruskal Wallis H)

Father's Occupation	n	Mean Rank	sd	$\bar{X}$	P	Significant difference
Self-employment	81	118.36				
Private sector	50	131.51	2	7.23	0.27*	Between self-employment and civil officer
Civil officer	127	135.81				

p<0.05*

When we look at the evaluation of the father occupation and the expectations from the sport, it is seen that there is a significant difference in favor of those fathers who are self-employed p<0.05.

4. Discussion

Orienteering takes the first place among the sport branches that are in demand both in Turkey and the world recently. There are various factors encouraging for doing orienteering as in the other sport branches. In this study, the aim is to state the significance level of the factors encouraging for orienteering. Having looked at the findings got in this study, the effect of friends and peer group on encouraging in doing sports is on the first rank with the 1. level. Çon et al (1997) state that primarily group of friends, family, sport clubs, physical education teachers, and the sports facilities of schools have most effect on encouraging people to do Akandere et al., (2009) state that social circle and financial situation have effect on starting and succeeding sports.

Bayraktar and Sunay (2007) claim that physical education teacher has the effect on encouraging people in volleyball at the first level, while Şimşek and Gökdemir (2006) claim the same thing for high school students in terms of athleticism branch. In this study, it is found out that the physical education teacher has an effect on encouraging to do sports at the 2. level.

In the study, it is stated that television channels don't have much effect on encouraging people to do sports, as in the study which was applied to different sample groups in the literature that also states that media organs have little effect on it (Salman ve Sunay, 2012., Bayraktar ve Sunay, 2007., Sunay ve Saraçoğlu, 2003., Kara ve Pular, 2003., Atlı ve ark. 2018). Moreover, in the study it is seen that family members' effect is at the 3. level among the factors impacting the encouragement to do sports. However, on the contrary to our study, it is stated in the literature that family has the most effect on encouraging to do sports. (Bayraktar and Sunay, 2007, Ölçücü et al., 2012, Ölçücü et al., 2014, Arpa, 2014, Sunay and Saraçoğlu, 2003, Özbek and Şanlı, 2011, Salman and Sunay 2012, Yıldırım and Sunay 2009). As to Arslan (2012) he claims in the study he applied to female football players that the interest, ability, and love in this sport branch, and the aim to get college education are the primary reasons. Wolfonden and Holt (2005) point out in the study they performed about the tennis that families, trainers and the sporters' acting altogether as a team brings the success in tennis.

In our study, having looked at the significance level of the reasons for doing orienteering, it is seen that interest in the sport comes at the 1. level, delighting at the 2.level, and the awareness of the positive contributions of the sport at the 3.level. It can be said that the sport which is performed willingly has some contributions like bringing along continuousness and success alongside with teaching how to use time more efficiently and quick decision making. Beside, delighting in succeeding also has great effect on doing orienteering. The sports that are performed individually in nature are more embraced by people nowadays. Each success reinforces the sporters' competitor identity and is a source of motivation for the sporters when it is known by the society. Developing self-confidence becomes more prominent in orienteering. Having looked at the distribution of the reasons of doing orienteering, it is seen that the interest is at the first place. The studies applied to different sample groups in the literature support the results of our study (Arslan et al., 2017., Alibaz et al., 2006., Bayraktar and Sunay, 2007., Ölçücü et al, 2012, Salman and Sunay, 2012., Yıldırım and Sunay, 2009). It is pointed out that people have different expectations from the sport branches and these expectations are associated with various factors.

Having looked at the importance level of expectations, it is seen that to attend national team comes at the 1. level, to be and keep healthy comes at the 2.level, and to be a good sporter and make a living out of sports at the 3. level. In the literature studies as well which support our study, to become a national team player is placed at the top (Binboğa ve ark., 2013, Salman ve Sunay, 2012). In this study, the aim of the sporters doing orienteering to be a referee comes last. In the study performed by Atlı et al., (2017), also had the same results. In our study, there was a significant difference between the reasons for doing orienteering and the education levels of fathers $p < 0.05$. There was a negative connection between the education level of fathers and the reasons for doing this sport. There was a significant difference between the reasons for doing this sport and the fathers' occupations. It has been observed that those whose father is a self-employed are more inclined to do orienteering. In the study Yücel et al., (2015) performed, the place, level of the parents' education and income, the feeding behaviours and some other factors are more effective in choosing sports branches. As a result, it has been seen that there are various factors for encouraging people to orienteering in Turkey. The orienteering done in different categories in our country has gained speed with weekend activities especially in big cities. The effect of friend and peer groups on encouraging in doing sports at the 1.level is also an indicator. Among the reasons of doing the sport, liking the sport is also an important indicator. Being a nature sport enables it to be performed willingly and with pleasure.

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